

Prospects for the Development of Lending Practices in Russian Banks

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Abstract: *Currently, the practice of digitalization in all types of activities is becoming a problem. In the activities of similar banks, improving the practice of lending to individuals remains the main requirement.*

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In recent years, there has been a clear trend of Russian banks to increase the level of customer service and expand the services offered. This applies to corporate clients, small and medium-sized businesses, and retail. First of all, this is due to the dynamics of life and the dynamics of doing business, the need to save as much time as possible. The saying "Time is money" is more relevant than ever. Banks are implementing new technologies in their service quite dynamically and at a high level. The main direction of development is IT technologies that allow customers to use banking products remotely and save their time. At the same time, an opportunity has opened up in the implementation of services that were not typical for the banking sector before. The quality of services has significantly improved, and customers no longer need to visit financial institutions as often as before. Remote banking service (RBS) is a general term for technologies for providing banking services based on orders transmitted by the client remotely, that is, without his visit to the bank [1, p.23]. Such technologies are classified according to the way financial information is transmitted by the service provider. Information transmission methods are differentiated by technical solutions and communication channels. Technologies for corporate clients and individuals are distinguished by subject affiliation: - electronic banking for corporate clients; - electronic banking for individuals. The main classification of RBS technologies is based on the types of information systems (software and hardware) used for banking operations. As an example, consider the types of RBS services provided by Gazenergobank JSC: - Phone-Bank

- **Client-Bank.** - Internet Banking – - ATMs, terminals. The implementation of remote services depends on the type of client: private clients, small and medium-sized businesses, corporate clients. E-banking and Telephone service are available for private clients. With the help of E-Bank, customers can: - track the status of their accounts and cards in real time; - perform operations with Visa and MasterCard plastic cards; - perform monthly repayment of a loan received from the bank, make applications for partial early repayment of the loan; - buy and sell currency at a favorable bank rate- add funds to your accounts to perform operations on the Forex market; - pay for mobile communications, Internet, TV, housing and utilities, telephone, e-wallets, etc.; - make intrabank and any ruble transfers, etc. By connecting to the Telephone

Remote Service, the bank's customers get the opportunity to quickly access their accounts (around the clock): – get advice on all products and services of the bank; - fill out a loan and credit card application form; - make payments for using the services and make a number of other money transfers; – get data on the status of your accounts, transactions made, order account statements, find out the amount of accounts payable; – transfer money to a plastic card. For small businesses, the bank offers the following types of RBS: – "Phone-Bank – - a round-the-clock multi-channel electronic operator that informs about account balances. - "Client-Bank". - "Internet Client-Bank". By connecting to the Client-Bank and Internet–Client-Bank systems, customers can: - Accept payment orders around the clock. - Carry out payment orders accepted on Mon-Fri from 9: 00 to 16: 00, the day of sending. – Use previously created payment orders as templates. - Make requests for bank statements. - Conduct currency transactions. - Create a directory of correspondents and employees. - Exchange data between the Client-Bank and BS 1with:Enterprise, BS Parus. Development – BSS "ДБО RBO BS-Client v.3» и R-Style Software Lab «InterBank RS». For corporate clients, the bank offers similar services: Telephone service for corporate clients – the ability to receive data on the status of the organization's accounts, as well as receive the latest information about the bank's products and services. It should be noted that this service is not popular among both categories of legal entities and it is used by a very small number of the bank's clients. System "Internet-Client-Bank" allows clients to receive the following types of services - ability to manage accounts with the provision of full-fledged payment documents - provision of statements at the client's request about the status of accounts, cash flow - getting balance data, overdraft information;

- exchange of information with the bank via chats and bots. When providing Internet banking and Bank-Client services, Gazenergobank JSCuses an automated system developed by BSS LLC - "RBO BS-Client v. 3" (a comprehensive integrated solution that includes the entire range of banking services provided outside the bank's office). In general, the following main problems of development of RBS channels can be identified in Russia: 1. Unpopularity and underdevelopment of non-cash forms of payments among the population. 2. Customers' distrust of banks. 3. Low income of the population. 4. Low level of financial culture of the population. 5. Technical savvy of clients. 6. The level of implementation of modern information systems and technologies by the management of credit institutions. 7. Legal restrictions. 8. Underdeveloped communication infrastructure in the regions. 9. High cost of RBS implementation for the bank. 10. Insufficient number of online payment recipients. 11. Organization of security and related issues. The transition from the classical form of banking to remote banking will require a significant change in the minds of consumers. This is a long and complex process, as it will require significant efforts from banks to overcome consumers' distrust and fear of remote banking services as a universal financial management tool. The question of the cost and profitability of the RBS system is ambiguous. Experts say that the cost of implementing remote service systems consists of several components, but in the end, the choice of supplier plays a crucial role, as well as measures to ensure the security of payments. The most expensive part of implementing RBS systems is monitoring and organizing the security of operations performed – such funds are not cheap for banks not only during the initial implementation, but also require constant capital investment and improvement during the operational phase. The cost of implementation depends on the quality of the components: the development of the system structure itself, the popularity and authority of the developer's brand, the level and volume of features provided. Also important is the payback of RBS systems, the time for which RBS systems will start to make a profit. The profit from RBS systems is indirect. It is more profitable to serve customers remotely, rather than through offices, for example, using smartphone apps. For this reason, many banks are currently reducing the number of offices and employees. Service costs are reduced, and the level of service increases, creating more

convenient and comfortable conditions for customers. It is worth noting that banks ' revenue from remote services is growing due to an increase in cross-sales, thanks to prompt notification of customers about new products and services, as well as targeted offers and contextual targeted advertising. There is an increase in additional income related to sales of services provided by bank partners. For example, construction and insurance companies or travel companies.

List of sources used:

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